

StandICT.eu 2023
ICT STANDARDISATION OBSERVATORY AND SUPPORT FACILITY IN EUROPE

EUOS Standards Academy – *Training the Next Generation of ICT Standards Experts*

Webinar, Jun 13 '23

StandICT.eu has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement **No. 951972**.

Technical Working Groups x 6
(AI, Blockchain, Cyber, Smart Cities, Trusted Info, Data Spaces)

Standards Academy →

Join the conversation and bring your contributions to the ICT Standards Community by starting new discussions on a selected topic, creating a focus group or sharing your insights.

Standards Academy: Our remit

Scope

Education on the **why** and the **how** of standards & standardization

Terms of reference

- Institute an Expert Group for the term 2021 - 2023
- ***Curate and make available educational and training materials on the standardization process***
 - ***Leverage existing material – not creating new***
- Consider all types of standards development organisations and methods
 - *There is a role for all*
- Consider all stakeholder types
 - *Policy makers, industry, academia, societal orgs*
- Recommend a set of deliverables and associated timelines
- Report progress to EAG on regular basis and present updates to StandICT workshops annually

Standards Academy V HSBooster

StandICT.eu & Hsbooster.eu Academy
What's in the GA

 HSBooster.eu
Horizon Standardisation Booster

 HSBooster.eu
Horizon Standardisation Booster

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Task 5.1 - HSBooster.eu will deliver an **online Standards Academy** designed specifically for projects. Training will be delivered both through online materials, 20+ training sessions (modules), and events such as 6 webinars.

Material included in the academy may also include content from SDOs or other relevant sources.

The (eLearning) training packages are prepared with available material and specific courses created in this task as needed, for **beginners, intermediate, and advanced levels**.

Task 4.2 - To create a **repository of standards education information** and provide workshops and webinars (utilising the webinar organisational support provided in Task 4.1) to help bootstrap next generation standards developers (integrating previous work from CEN-CENELEC's Joint Working Group on Education about Standardisation' (JWG-EaS) with the research agenda of European Academy for Standardisation (EURAS), ETSI Educatio.

Existing engagements with standards bodies NSAI, BSI, DIN, SFS, DS, AS and UNE on Education about Standardisation will be integrated into the task

Draw a first Draft document to pinpoint important aspects as:

- Differentiation and similarities of the 2 platforms
 - Justification of the effort
- Underline the plus-points of the Hsbooster.eu Academy (improved structure and accessibility for users)
 - Sustainability: what happens when the project is over and how the material will be handles

Expert Group: who we are

Status	Name/Org	Expertise/Affiliation
Active	● Brian McAuliffe (Chair)	Member of StandICT EAG; ISO/IEC JTC 1 Liaison Officer to EC
Active	● Ray Walshe	Chair, StandICT EAG
Observing	● Paul Killeen	DG CNECT, European Commission
Active	● David Filip	ISO/IEC JTC 1 PAS Mentor and Systems Integration Facilitator
Observing	● Chiara Giovannini	Deputy General Secretary, ANEC
Observing	● Cyrill Dirscherl	Ex DG GROW, European Commission (recently retired)
Active	● Ivana Mijatovic	Education Lead, EURAS
Active	● Nikolaos Myriounis	Chair, NATO Standardization Management Group/Education Panel
TBD	● ETSI	
Active	● Martin Chapman	Director, Technology & Standards Policy, DigitalEurope
Active	● Andriana Prentza	OASIS Open Europe
Active	● Signe Annette Bøgh	Consultant, Danish Standards
Active	● Natalia Giorgi	Standardisation Consultant, European Trade Union Confederation
Active	● Pam Tarif	Head of Global Engagement, ECOS
Active	● Amelie Leipprand	Senior Project Manager, Member Services & Young Professionals, DIN
Observing	● Ian Gardner	Head of Academy & Capacity Building, IEC

SDO

Societal

Industry

Academia

Gov/Policy

Building the repository

EUOS Academy – Deliverables

- Define knowledge, skills, competences required for various stakeholder types
- Within each stakeholder type there are sub-types e.g.
 - HEI: students, management, lecturers
 - Companies: Executive leadership, management, technical staff, other staff e.g. legal, GA

Table 1. To be continued: Draft plan for working on (IT) standardisation knowledge, skills, competence and expertise matrix for the various user/stakeholder types as a base for developing educational pathways for each user type

Stakeholders		Definitions of			
Organizations	Focus on	<p>Knowledge: "the outcome of the assimilation of information through learning. Knowledge is the body of facts, principles, theories, and practices that is related to a field of work or study. In the context of the European Qualification Framework, knowledge is described as theoretical and/or factual"¹</p>	<p>Skill: "the ability to apply knowledge and use know-how to complete tasks and solve problems. In the context of the European Qualification Framework, skills are described as cognitive (involving the use of logical, intuitive, and creative thinking) or practical (involving manual dexterity and the use of methods, materials, tools, and instruments)"</p>	<p>Competence: "the proven ability to use knowledge, skills, and personal, social and/or methodological abilities, in work or study situations, and in professional and personal development"</p>	<p>Expertise: "continuous learning characterized by the constant acquisition of knowledge, reorganization of information, and progressive problem-solving" (Hertig, 2000) often "does not meet the scholarly criteria for the expertise (competence, added by IM) (research and theory)" (Swanson, 2007 "expertise is a dynamic state, domain-specific, and the key components of expertise are knowledge, experience, and problem-solving</p>
	Academics (teachers, lecturers)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who are (IT) standardization teachers? • What is body of knowledge needed for teaching standardization? • How to connect standardization research with teaching? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to teach about standards and standardization • Active teaching methods • How to teach skills needed for standardization? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to define teaching outcomes in standardization • Standardization <u>competence based</u> teaching 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bringing standardization practice into the classroom - how to sustain interest and how to overcome difference? • Connecting with standardization practice
Higher education institutions (HEIs)	Students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Content 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How to define 	

Building the repository

- Existing frameworks identified
- APEC Guideline 6 (2019)
- ISO International Workshop Agreement (2019)

APEC SCSC Education Guideline 6
Inspiring Next Generation of Standards Professional Development - Phase 2

Career Roadmap and Competence Requirements for Standards Professionals

Part 1. In Companies

Part 2. In Standards-related Organizations

*APEC Sub-Committee on Standards and Conformance (SCSC)
August 2019*

INTERNATIONAL
WORKSHOP
AGREEMENT

**IWA
30-2**

First edition
2019-10

**Competence of standards
professionals —**

**Part 2:
In standards-related organizations**

Recommend knowledge *

- Knowledge of conformity assessment (testing, inspection and certification)
- Knowledge of drafting rules for company standards
- Knowledge of existing standards/technical regulations in a specified sector
- Knowledge of external standards related to products and technology
- Knowledge of international standardization activities and related organizations
- Knowledge of methodologies for performance management

Deliverable: Standards Academy Portal

<https://www.standict.eu/index.php/euos-academy>

The screenshot displays the EUOS Standards Academy portal. At the top left is the logo for EUOS Standards Academy, powered by StandICT.eu. Below the logo is a navigation bar with three buttons: "For *Beginners*", "For *intermediate users*", and "For *advanced users*". A link "Read more and find out which pack mostly suits your needs" is positioned below these buttons. The main heading reads "Browse the training catalogue and find the resources for your needs". On the left side, there is a search bar and a list of filters: Topic, Format, Level of expertise, Source, and Language, each with a dropdown arrow. A "Reset filters" button is located at the bottom of the filter list. The main content area shows "Showing 1 - 9 out of 24 training contents found". A resource card is displayed with the title "The Standardization Podcast by DIN". The card includes a description: "Human beings are not ants – What you never wanted to know about standardization, but definitely should know!". Metadata for the resource includes: TOPIC: Education, FORMAT: Other, LEVEL OF EXPERTISE: Entry level, LANGUAGE: English, and SOURCE: DIN. The creation date is listed as 18.01.23.

Standards Academy: Filters

Can enter keyword here optionally

Search

Topic ▾

Format ▾

Level of expertise ▾

Source ▾

Language ▾

Reset filters

Topic ^

- Communications
- Consortia
- Curricula
- Education
- Education - Cloned
- Environmental
- Europe
- Harmonised Standards
- Human Resources
- ICT
- Internet
- Internet - Cloned
- Interoperability
- IPR
- Legislation
- Management
- Open Source
- Open Standards
- Other
- PAS

more ...

Format ^

- Academic Paper
- Blog Post
- Book Chapter
- Book
- Conference Proceedings
- Interactive Web Content
- Report
- Training Course
- Video
- Webinar
- White Paper
- Other PDF
- Other

Source ^

- None
- 3GPP
- ANSI
- ASD-STAN
- ASTM
- ASTM
- ATIS
- CEN
- CEN/CENELEC
- CENELEC
- CIGI
- CSA
- DIF
- DIN
- DMTF
- Enterprise Ethereum
- ERCIM
- Ethereum Community

more ...

Language ^

- English
- French
- German
- Italian

Standards Academy: Starter Packs

Our selected starter packs

If you're new to the EOUS Standards Academy and need a bit of a guidance, you can find here our selected training contents to get you started. These starter packs have been created by our top trainers and are grouped to satisfy your needs, based on your level of expertise. Learn more from the boxes below and select the pack that mostly suits your needs!

For *beginners*

- How to use standards.
- How to take part in the standards making process.
- How to include standardisation from the beginning of a project or businesses.

Get started

For *intermediate users*

- Standard Development Organisations: how to get involved.
- Stakeholder engagement.
- How to reap the full benefits standardisation can offer.

Get started

For *advanced users*

- Participating in standardisation to influence the content of future standards.
- Role and responsibilities of Technical Committees & Working Groups.
- Harmonised Standards.

Get started

Standards Academy: Portal

RESOURCE

Standards and Open Source: Bringing them together

The aim of this EU-funded report is to analyse the collaboration models between Standards Development Organisations (SDOs) and Cloud Open Source software development initiatives, propose practical ways to further strengthen their interaction and t

CREATED ON: 13.01.23

TOPIC

Open Source

Open Standards

LANGUAGE

English

FORMAT

Report

LEVEL OF EXPERTISE

Intermediate, Advanced

SOURCE

Potential future deliverables

- (European-specific?) Competency matrices
 - Based upon APEC Guidelines, ISO IWA 30
 - For: Policy Makers, Industry, Public Administrations, Academia, Societal Stakeholders,
- Education pathways?
- Certifications/badges?
- Multiple languages

Thanks from

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